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Factors Affecting Tax Compliance Intentions: An Overview

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Abstract:

This study focuses on evaluating the previous literature on factors affecting individuals' tax compliance intentions (TCI). The studies were selected from 3 prestigious journals, namely LAW & POLICY, Journal of Business Ethics, and Journal of Economic Psychology in the period from 2000 to present. The results show that researchers are paying more attention to government factors such as power, justice, and trust rather than factors that represent personal emotions such as shame. Future studies should focus more on understanding the mechanism of the impact of individual emotion factors on individuals' TCI to get a better assessment.

Keywords: tax compliance intentions

1. Introduction

Tax is the main source of government revenue for public investment projects, social infrastructure construction, etc. In addition, this is also a source of government subsidies to support businesses and households to overcome the difficult period of the economy. In general, keeping the tax rate stable will contribute a lot to improving social welfare. However, not all individuals are willing to comply with taxes. The main purpose of tax evasion is to bring economic benefits to individuals. However, sometimes there are other factors that influence individuals' intentions to evade taxes, such as policy laxity or tax injustice. This will be further explored through this study.

2. Results

We collect articles about TCI based on related keywords like Tax compliance, Tax evasion, Tax avoidance, Tax morale. The selected journals are LAW & POLICY, Journal of Business Ethics (JBE), and Journal of Economic Psychology (JOEP), all of which are prestigious journals, and ranked SSCI Q1 by WOS and SJR. The results of the number of articles obtained from 2000 to now (Table 1) on tax compliance intentions for L&P are 8, JBE is 32 and JOEP is 58. However, not all studies can use it. can be used for analysis. We omitted firm-level studies, studies with only individual characteristics (such as income, age, etc.) factors, qualitative studies and non-experimental study. As a result, only 5 L&P journals, 10 JBE studies, and 34 JOEP studies were analyzed. Looking at the publication year of the studies in the 3 journals, it can be seen that the number of studies published in L&P is small and over a narrow period (2007-2014). The largest number of

studies were found in the journal JOEP with 35 articles and a wide time span (2001-2020). In addition, the 10 articles from the JBE journal used also have a long time span (2003-2022) and it is likely that the number of TCI studies published in this journal will increase in the future.

Table 1: Number of TCI studies in 3 journals

	Number	Selected	Publication year of the selected studies
LAW & POLICY	8	5	2007 – 2014
Journal of Business Ethics	32	8	2003 – 2022
Journal of Economic Psychology	58	34	2001 - 2020

Source: Author

Through the synthesis process, the author synthesizes a group of factors affecting the tax compliance intention of individuals as follows:

- *Shame*: can be explained as guilt when performing behaviors that are against morality and standards. This feeling can be formed before, during, or after the event.

- *Justice/fair/equity*: refers to the tax fairness (be it tax rates or penalties for tax evasion for different individuals) of competent stakeholders.

- *Norms*: represents socio-cultural factors, measured on different levels such as (individual, occupation, economic, nation, etc.).

- *Risk*: can be risk preferences, risk seeking, attitude to risk, etc.

- *Trust*: individuals feel that the government always works in an effective and reputable way and at the same time is always aiming for the common good.

- *Power*: power to monitor and manage compliance and impose sanctions on tax evasion. It can be expressed through law, legal, detectability and policy (fines, penalties).

- *Tax rate*: the tax rate that individuals must pay, which can be average tax or progressive tax.

An overview of the number of articles and detailed studies based on each factor is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Studies sorted by factors

Factor	LAW & POLICY		Journal of Business Ethics		Journal of Economic Psychology	
	Number	Detail	Number	Detail	Number	Detail
Shame	0		1	Okafor (2022)	2	Ashby et al. (2009); Coricelli et al. (2014)
Justice/ fair/ equity	3	Ahmed & Braithwaite (2007); Rechberger et al. (2010); Hartner et al. (2010)	2	Okafor (2022) Trivedi et al. (2003)	10	Cuccia & Carnes (2001); Kirchler & Maciejovsky (2001); Kim (2002); Kirchler et al. (2006); Verboon & van Dijke (2007); Van Dijke & Verboon (2010); Verboo & van Dijke (2011); Gobena & Van Dijke (2016); Pántya et al. (2016); Gobena & Van Dijke

						(2017)
Norms	0		3	Górecki & Letki (2021); Bobek et al. (2007); Bobek et al. (2012);	9	Wenzel (2004); Wenzel (2005a); Wenzel (2005b); Kirchler et al. (2006); Verboon & van Dijke (2007); Ashby et al. (2009); Hokamp (2014); Korndörfer et al. (2014); Garcia et al. (2020)
Risk	0		2	Molero & Pujol (2011); Trivedi et al. (2003)	4	Tan & Yim (2014); Pellizzari & Rizzi (2014); Bernasconi et al. (2014); Rodriguez-Justicia & Theilen (2018)
Trust	2	Wahl et al. (2010); Hofmann et al. (2014)	0		10	Alm & Torgler (2006); Van Dijke & Verboon (2010); Kogler, et al. (2013); Kastlunger et al. (2013); Prinz et al. (2014); Gobena & Van Dijke (2016); Gobena & Van Dijke (2017); Mendoza et al. (2017); Rodriguez-Justicia & Theilen (2018); Batrancea et al. (2019)
Power	1	Hofmann et al. (2014)	3	Górecki & Letki (2021); Maciejovsky et al. (2011); LaMothe, & Bobek (2020)	13	Webley et al. (2001); Kirchler, E., & Maciejovsky, B. (2001); Kirchler et al. (2006); Verboon & van Dijke (2007); Kastlunger et al. (2009); Alm et al. (2010); Kogler, et al. (2013); Kastlunger et al. (2013); Andrei et al. (2014); Prinz et al. (2014); Gobena & Van Dijke (2016); Mendoza et al. (2017); Batrancea et al. (2019)
Tax rate	0		1	Górecki & Letki (2021)	5	Alm et al. (2010); Bazart & Bonein (2014); Pellizzari & Rizzi (2014); Bernasconi et al. (2014); Mendoza et al. (2017)

Source: Author

It can be seen that the group of factors about power, justice, trust, and norms is of most interest to the researchers with a total of 17, 15, 12 and 12 respectively. These factors are mainly towards recognition of individuals about government, including trust in the government, perception of the authority of the government, and the fairness of the government. The norms factor is also widely understood because of its variety of aspects. The shame factor - representing individual factors, is studied relatively little with only one article in JBE and two articles in JOEP. Thus, it can be seen that researchers seem to be tending to overestimate the influence of the government on individuals' TCI. In fact, this is not necessarily true because emotions can directly influence individual actions before individuals are aware of external factors. Therefore, understanding the influence of Shame on TCI is essential for future studies.

3. Conclusion

Previous studies have discovered and explained a number of theoretical and practical issues related to individuals' TCI. Many factors affecting TCI have been proposed, with the most prominent being the group of factors about government, norms, and individual emotions. However, studies are drawing greater attention to the factors which are related to government actions. Meanwhile, the relationship between personal emotions (such as shame) and TCI is relatively limited. This research gap has opened up new research directions on TCI, especially in the context of developing countries. The consideration of individual factors, related to thoughts, feelings and ethics will provide other important perspectives for tax researchers. This will complement existing theories and help policymakers make more informed decisions in improving residents' TCI.

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